

INVESTIGATING FLOW MECHANICS WITHIN A NOVEL NON-DESTRUCTIVE INJECTABILITY MEASUREMENT FOR FIBRE PREFORMS

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ABSTRACT

Current trends in the field of Fibre Reinforced Plastics (FRP) are exceeding the capabilities of classical, recognised inspection and test methods. Novel non-destructive measurement methods to easily assess the quality assurance within an industrial mass production are required. The research undertaken by the Centre for Advanced Composite Materials is focused on a novel method to assess properties of textile reinforcements employed in Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) processes. This method non-destructively measures the resistance provided by textiles, stacks and preforms to compressive deformation and fluid flow. These two material properties are indicative for the success of a subsequent resin injection process and are therefore a crucial and characteristic quality control values.

On this basis a simple, mobile device is envisaged to support BMW Technology and Production staff to evaluate the injectability and compressibility properties of stacks and preforms. Such a device gives instant feedback, to identify changes in properties from batch to batch. Compaction response has been studied extensively in the literature, with measurements being conceptually simple, and easily applicable in a non-destructive format. Flow resistance of fibre reinforcements, or “injectability”, is commonly quantified by permeability. Rather than calculating permeability using traditional methods (destructive preparation of samples, infusion with a liquid), simple measures of injectability of textile reinforcements are determined using an air pulse applied within the stack or preform. The air pulse provides reliable and immediate information about injectability, enabling fast and accurate measurement methods with simple sensor requirements, suitable for quality assessments within an industrial production environment. Advancing techniques for material characterisation and material failure detection is the main goal of this research.

1 INTRODUCTION

Simple and easy to interpret measures are a requirement for the acceptance of a quality control system within an industrial production environment [1]. This is particularly true for the manufacturing of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) and their semi-finished products (i.e. textiles, preforms). Current trends in the field of fibre reinforced plastics are exceeding the capabilities of classical, recognised inspection and test methods [2]. Novel non-destructive measurement methods to easily assess the quality assurance within an industrial mass production are required. The competitiveness and profitability of CFRP parts is mainly restricted due to their high manufacturing costs. Figure 1 illustrates the breakdown costs for production of a generic CFRP part through Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). The material costs are the main driver to the overall costs for the final CFRP part. Rejection rates and cut-offs must be reduced to strengthen the effectiveness of production and increase the competitive position of CFRP.

Semi-finished textiles offer, as every kind of fabric does, a high natural variation due to a variety of processing steps and complex sub-processes during their manufacturing. This high natural variation poses particular challenges and raises the demand for comprehensive quality assurance systems throughout the entire process chain to guarantee stable processes and low rejection rates. Nonetheless,

the implementation and application of quality systems for a highly automated industrial production line to produce high quality CFRP are still at an early stage and require novel quality measurement tools.

Figure 1: Costs Analysis for a generic CFRP produced through RTM; Quantity: 25,000 [3]

Current non-destructive (ND) measurement tools are restricted in their capabilities to monitor the mass production of CFRP parts. The evaluation and characterisation of multi-ply stacks and preforms is especially limited with the available techniques. To overcome this issue, the Centre for Advanced Composites Materials is developing a non-destructive quality monitoring system to assess the injectability and compressibility in local planar regions of carbon fibre stacks and 3D preforms.

This paper is focused on the development of methods to non-destructively assess the resistance provided by textiles, stacks and preforms to compressive deformation and fluid flow. Fast methods are developed without the requirement for cutting of samples, and which have outputs that are easily interpreted by non-experts. While compressibility-measures are relatively easy to define, the inability to cut samples significantly hampers the direct measurement of permeability.

Before the introduction of non-destructive injectability measurements, the majority of the permeability measurements employed to indicate the quality of a semi-finished textile were completed in a destructive manner. Existing methods are focused on accurate characterisation for process simulation, and are too expensive (destruction of products, overly time intensive) to be utilised for quality assessment in an industrial environment [4].

2 NON-DESTRUCTIVE QUALITY ASSESSMENT, APPLICATION AND LIMITATIONS

The ND quality assessment of semi-finished textiles is a key objective for an effective and reliable production for CFRPs. In particular, permeability and compaction response have been shown to be very influential on the subsequent resin injection process [5]. In addition, permeability and compaction response are important material properties for process simulation and design [6]. However, existing methods to measure these quantities are time intensive and laboratory based. In the context of material quality assessment, the limitations are:

- If performed destructively, sample cutting leads to the destruction of the semi-product, at significant cost.
- Relocation of samples to a remote laboratory causes significant time delays.
- Measurements are detailed, time consuming, and the results are not easily interpreted by non-experts.

These limitations motivate the development of a fast, non-destructive characterisation technique (see Figure 2), which can be performed at the production line, or possibly inline within processing equipment. If measurements can be performed directly on semi-finished textiles without altering any property of the product (non-destructive), the following significant benefits are realised:

- Immediate feedback is provided by measurements made at the production line, to help staff identify the causes of failures in production.
- The measurement method detects changes and failures within the process chain due to changes of product conditions and primary material changes.
- The measurement method is ready for “smart production” and “Industry 4.0”.
- Characterised products can be reinserted into the remainder of the process chain, to directly correlate measured properties to the success of subsequent manufacture.
- Time and cost savings allow for efficient qualification of new material sources, and qualification of new production equipment.
- If implemented inline, 100 % testing of the products is possible, allowing for detailed analysis of cause and effect through the process chain.

Figure 2: Determination of (a) Permeability vs. (b) Injectability

A prototype has been developed to detect different material features by interpreting injectability and compressibility of the tested preforms and stacks. The application of the novel non-destructive measurement method looks promising from first field trials. This so-called Non-destructive Preform Tester (NDPT) was developed in cooperation with the BMW AG to monitor the quality of semi-finished products.

For the very first time, a 100 percent quality and process monitoring system can be implemented within a CFRP manufacturing line to support the production of multi-ply semi-finished textiles. Process limits can be defined to assist preventive maintenance, detect wear or other issues causing production problems. Cause-and-effect relations between the process and semi-products can be assessed, intervention limits determined and preventive maintenance supported. In contrast to already acknowledged and more complex quality monitoring techniques (e.g. eddy current, permeability determination) the proposed method is ready for “Smart Production” and “Industry 4.0”.

Figure 3 shows the capabilities of the developed method compared to previously available ND measurement and test methods for validating the quality of semi-finished products and CFRP parts. ND

test methods can be classified according to their physical principles. As can be seen from the figure, the injectability measurement tool presented in this paper offers enhanced capabilities over previously-used systems.

		Physical Principal			Electromagnetic			Thermography		Acoustic		Mechanical		
		Radiography			Visual									
		X-Ray inspection	X-Ray refraction	Computer tomography	Eddy Current	Visual Examination	Particle penetrant inspection	Laser Triangulation	Active Thermography	Passive Thermography	Ultrasound scan	Acoustic resonance	Permeability	Injectability
Application	2D-Semi textile	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓					✓	✓
	3D-Semi textile	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓								✓
	CFRP-Part	✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		
Feature Detection	Inhomogeneities	+	o	o	o	+	o	o	+	+	+	o	+	+
	Foreign particles	+	o	+	-	+	-	o	o		+	o	-	-
	Voids	+	+	+	o	o	o	-	+	+	+	-		
	Fibre Volume Fraction	+		+				o	-	-	+	-	+	+
	Fibre Orientation		-	o	o	o		+	-	-	-		-	-
Process rel. criteria	Investment costs	o		-	o	+	o	o	o		o	o	+	+
	Low Qualification	o	-	-	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	-	+
	Contactless	+	+	+	-	o	+		+	+	o	-	-	-
	Fast	-	-	-	o	o	o		-	+	o		-	+
	Mobility	o					+	-			o		-	+
	Industrial robustness					+		+	-	-	+	-	o	+
Information	Quality of Information	+	+		-		-	o	+	-	+	-	+	o
	Plane Measurement			+			+		+	+	-	+	+	+
	Direct Feedback	+			-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+
	Image	+	o	-	o	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	o	o
	Objective assessment			+		-	+	o	o	o			+	+
Concl.	+	8	3	6	0	6	5	3	7	7	7	1	6	10
	o	3	3	2	7	5	5	7	4	2	5	4	2	2
	-	1	3	4	4	1	3	3	4	2	3	7	7	3

Key

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Applicable	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Positive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Negative
<input type="checkbox"/>	Not Applicable	<input type="checkbox"/>	Mediocre		

Figure 3: Comparison of certain ND measurement systems [7]; final column added for this paper

A major benefit of the proposed injectability measurement when compared to established ND testing methods is the fast and easy-to-interpret measures produced, and the robustness of the technique. Compared to other measurement methods such as computer tomography or X-ray inspection, the results generated by the injectability measurements can easily be transferred to quantitative values enabling real time process control. The proposed measurement method is also flexible and easy to implement in an existing production environment at reasonable costs. The physical principle is relatively simple compared to other methods, but is easy to implement within existing facilities and suitable within a mass production environment.

2.1 Measurement Principle

In the proposed method, the textile product is compressed to a certain target thickness between two flat plates, while monitoring the required force of compaction. A transient air pressure pulse, impinged by a pressure reservoir, is then applied to determine injectability. Two different plate sets are utilised to measure either in-plane, or through-thickness injectability. Compaction response has been studied extensively, with measurements being conceptually simple, and easily applicable in a non-destructive format [8]. Here, compaction response is measured as a mode force (or modal force) at target thickness after a brief period of relaxation. The so-called mode force represents the most representative value after reaching the target thickness before injecting air.

As mentioned above, non-destructive measurement of permeability is problematic. Pure in-plane flow cannot be established, as holes cannot be cut into the semi-finished textile to ensure in-plane flow. Through-thickness measurements are influenced by the inability to seal the edges of the measurement area. Of particular relevance are relatively high velocities of the test fluid at the inlet of the measurement plates, and the complex 3D flow through the injection point and sample. Considering these limitations, permeability values are not the objective of the measurements presented here. New definitions of injectability are required and established, based on transient air flows within two different geometries. The aim is to assess an “average in-plane injectability” with one tool, and the “through-thickness injectability” with another. However, purely in-plane, or through-thickness flow cannot be achieved without sample cutting. The limitations and applicability of the new injectability measurement are explored in this paper through correlations to traditional permeability measurements.

Figure 4: Schematic of In-plane and Through-thickness injectability flow geometries.

Figure 4 schematically demonstrates the flow through the in-plane and through-thickness plate sets when a defect, such as a fold, is present. The influence of the defect on the pressure trace during the air injection phase is demonstrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Pressure decay data from In-plane measurements with and without features

Here, pressure was measured through a pressure transducer (Festo SPAB, -1 to +1 bar) attached to the gas reservoir. Assessment of the pressure trace reveals reliable information about the injectability of the tested textile. Several measures of injectability are possible and have been defined in previously published conference paper [9].

Preceding research has also demonstrated that the decay of pressure at the tool inlet can be described by an exponential function. The pressure decay is an exponential function of time and pressure.

$$p(t) = a \cdot e^{-(b \cdot t)} \quad (1)$$

Eqn. (1) defines the exponential function and its associated pressure decay factor b , which quantifies the rate of decay of the pressure curve. If pressure is plotted on a logarithmic scale a linear function is revealed, with the pressure decay factor b describing the slope of the linear curve. Here, this slope is used as an indicator for the resistance due to fluid flow, the injectability of the tested sample. The correlation to more classical permeability values is demonstrated in Section 2.2.

Figure 6: Pressure decay plot on a logarithmic scale for a representative sample

Figure 6 shows the measured pressure decay for a representative sample and its associated exponential fit plotted on a logarithmic scale. The exponential fit demonstrates a very good correlation close to 1 compared to the actual pressure decay. The small deviation can be explained by the initial and rapid pressure drop filling the tubing and a small cavity inside the measurement head.

2.2 Correlating Injectability to Permeability

The correlation of injectability and permeability provides detailed information about the presented definition and validity of injectability. The investigation is part of an ongoing study to assess the flow mechanics during the air injection. Here, only the correlation data will be presented, which demonstrates the significance of injectability measurements compared to classical permeability values.

The study was carried out at laboratory scale at the University of Auckland. Due to the non-destructive character of the methodology, multiple target thicknesses (see Section 3.1) are used to demonstrate the sensitivity of the measurement method. At least 10 samples (stack type A, see Section 3.1) were tested. First, samples were assessed by determining the injectability and compressibility from in-plane measurements. Subsequently the same samples were characterised using more traditional destructive permeability measurement technique, to explore the correlation to the measured air injectability. The sample size for the non-destructive tests was 100 x 100 mm, with a measurement being possible at three fibre volume fractions (V_f) with each sample. A transient air pulse was applied with an initial injection pressure of 90 kPa. The in-plane measurement heads have a 60 mm outer diameter.

In-plane permeability has been determined using a radial flow, steady state filling method with a constant injection pressure. The permeability measurements were undertaken with the same samples used for the injectability determination. To assure defined boundaries, the samples (100 x 100 mm) were cut to a defined geometry with an outer radius of 60 mm and an inner radius of 10 mm in accordance to the measurement head's geometry. The average in-plane permeability, k , is calculated utilising using Darcy's law:

$$\mathbf{q} = -\frac{K}{\mu} \cdot \nabla P \quad (2)$$

The stack was compressed to the target thickness using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) and then injected with oil (Mobil DTE Heavy Oil, $T = 21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\mu = 0.262 \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$). The mass flow rate was recorded with a digital scale measuring the mass loss throughout the measurement. The measurement was started after the air was completely driven out of the sample and only oil streamed through the textile. The inlet pressure was controlled using an automatic pressure transducer and held constantly at 80 kPa (absolute pressure). The oil temperature was monitored with a thermocouple (Type K). In addition, oil pressure was measured directly at the inlet to guarantee an accurate permeability calculation

3 Experimental Program

This section provides details about the experimental program completed during on-site studies at the BMW production plant in Landshut, Germany. It also provides additional information where the non-destructive measurement method was used during the first field trials.

3.1 Test Material

Different stack types have been assessed, each formed from multiple layers of a 300 g/m² carbon fibre non-crimp fabric (unidirectional). Within the presented studies two layups were considered (denoted as A and B in Table 1), which were tested at different thicknesses and nominal V_f .

<i>Stack</i>	<i>Layup</i>	<i>Target Thickness (mm)</i>	<i>Fibre Volume Fraction</i>
A	+45°/-45°/0°/90°/0°/90°/0°/-	3.44	Low
	45°/+45	3.12	Medium
	All 330 g/m ²	2.86	High
B	+45/0/-45/0/-45/0/-45 All ±45° 300 g/m ² All 0° 150 g/m ²	2.5	Process thickness

Table 1: Definitions of stack layups, and target conditions

3.2 Reference Measurements

Experiments were carried out to validate the variability of the tested materials by assessing the injectability and compressibility from stack to stack. The tested samples were preprocessed like other stacks from the series production and offer comparable inhomogeneities due to material and process variation. 11 Samples were tested. The investigation was done on fresh stacks (type B) without any pre-compaction.

3.3 Feature Detection on 2D Semi-Finished Products

This investigation shows the capabilities of the NDPT to differentiate between different material features. The investigation was done on fresh stacks (type B) without any pre-compaction. Two feature types were artificially created to validate general abilities of the measurement method to detect local changes in the V_f . Different characteristic gaps and folds (see Table 2) were introduced between the first and the second ply. Injectability and compressibility was measured with the feature placed in the middle

of the measurement head. Tests were performed with the NDPT on 12 samples with the same feature. The modal force was plotted against the pressure decay factor b as an injectability measure.

Gap width (mm)	Vf's -1 ply	Fold length (mm)	Vf's +1 ply	Vf's +2 plies	Vf's +3 plies
	5		5	5	5
10	10	10	10	10	
15	15	15	15	15	
20	20	20	20	20	

Table 2: Introducing features into the stacks; Reference stack layup B

3.4 Industrial Implementation – On-site Measurements

An on-site measurement series was performed accompanying the CFRP production in Landshut to validate the industrial capabilities of the NDPT and its measurement method. Here, the NDPT was used as a quality control tool between the preforming and the RTM step (Figure 7). Preforming is a crucial process within the CFRP RTM process chain, in which the stack will be formed into a stiffer 3D shaped preform enabling the final resin injection and improving the handling within automated processes. 112 preforms were tested as part of this investigation. The measurement position was maintained constant from preform to preform. The layup of the measured preforms differs from the previous experiments. Due to confidentiality reasons, no further information can be provided. The NDPT determined and recorded the b factor and the modal force from preform to preform. The confidence interval (95%), the mean, the standard deviation and the twofold standard deviation of the measurement values were determined. In addition, process windows of threefold standard deviation were calculated. Parts above or below the process windows were then visually assessed.

Figure 7: Implementation and application of the NDPT

4 Results and Discussion

This section demonstrates the capabilities of the measurement method within an industrial mass production environment. Basic liquid based permeability measurements were carried out and correlated to the previously defined injectability measures to verify that the measurement method provides a relevant measure of resin flow resistance within a textile reinforcement.

The ND measurement method was then integrated within the BMW production facilities for CFRP. First field trials were performed with the NDPT at the BMW plant Landshut. Section 4.2 presents the reference measurements to assess and evaluate the natural variability of the tested material. In Section 4.3 the tested material was manipulated to demonstrate the capability of the NDPT to detect features

that may be introduced during the preforming process. Finally, the NDPT was used as an online quality assessment tool within the production environment.

4.1 Correlating Injectability to Permeability

Figure 8 presents the measured average in-plane permeabilities against injectability, i.e. the pressure decay factor b in Eqn. 1. The dataset has been fitted with a linear correlation, and the R^2 value is provided as a measure of the quality of correlation. A very good correlation is demonstrated with a R^2 values of 0.97. Previous experiments have shown a similar correlation for the through thickness permeability [9].

Figure 8: Correlation of Permeability to Injectability

4.2 Reference Measurements

Figure 8 presents measurement on variability of the tested materials, by assessed via injectability and compressibility from stack to stack. Each sample is represented by a red marker, whereas the average of all the samples is denoted by the grey marker. The pressure decay factor b 0.047 for the in-plane measurements. Due to differences regards the head's injection geometry, the through thickness injectability is noticeable higher with 0.47. It can be noted that the injectability varies by 18 % for the in-plane measurements and 16 % for the through-thickness measurement whereas the force varies consistently by 6 % for the in-plane and through-thickness measurement.

Figure 9: Material variation measured with the NDPT

4.3 Feature Detection on 2D Semi-Finished Products

The results shown in Figure 10 verify that the measurement method is capable of detecting and differentiating different types of features. In particular, the in-plane measurements provide a good trend, where locally higher V_f 's lead to reduced injectability of the preform. However, the through-thickness measurement is harder to evaluate. It seems that increasing the local V_f 's leads to a situation where air passes faster through or at least out of the material. One explanation for this phenomenon can be found by considering the open edges of this measurement method. It seems that air goes sideways out of the textile instead of through the textile.

Figure 10: Characterised preform features with the NDPT

4.4 Industrial Implementation – On-site Measurements

The relevant data of this investigation is presented in Figure 11. Preform numbers 88 and 97 generated values above the previously defined process windows. Part number 97 showed an abnormally high injectability whereas the compressive force is noticeably low. Part 88 behaves in the opposite manner, exhibiting a high compaction force along with a relatively low injectability.

A visual inspection of these preforms revealed that part 97 contained a strong waviness in ply two and some significant gaps in ply two and four, explaining the measurement results. Part 88 requires a higher compaction force than the average and has therefore a reduced injectability. A visual inspection showed densifications in ply 4 and fold in ply 5, as shown in Figure 11.

The compaction force varies throughout the measured preforms with 1232.10 N, whereas the b-factor's variation is 0.493. This shows the variability the preform step is introducing and complexity of process chain.

Figure 11: On-site real part measurements

5 CONCLUSION

The prototype preform injectability and compressibility tester, developed and delivered to the commercial partner in late 2016, is currently assessed by BMW as part of field trials. For the very first time a non-destructive measurement method to determine injectability and compressibility of semi-finished textiles has been trialed in a mass production environment. The potential of the measurement method was proven. The prototype detects different material features as demonstrated in Section 4.3, by analysing injectability and compressibility of semi-finished textiles. Here, the pressure decay, b , is an indicator for gaps and other features that locally reduce V_f . The force measurement provides a suitable indicator for local densification of the tested material. These trials have demonstrated the industrial capabilities of the measurement method and future potential as a non-destructive quality measurement tool for semi-finished textiles. Process limits can be assessed and defined to assist preventive maintenance, detect wear or other issues causing production problems.

For the first time, a 100 percent quality and process monitoring system for multi-ply semi-finished textiles can be realised within a CFRP manufacturing line. Cause-effect relations between the process and semi-products can be assessed, intervention limits determined and preventive maintenance supported. In contrast to already acknowledged and more complex quality monitoring techniques (e.g. eddy current, permeability determination) the proposed method is ready for “Smart Production” and “Industry 4.0”.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Chiarini, *Understanding the Lean Enterprise*. Springer Cham Heidelberg New York Dordrecht London, 2016.
- [2] MAI Carbon Cluster Management GmbH, Spitzencluster für die Zukunft der CFK-Großserientechnologie|Leading-Edge Cluster for the future of carbon composites, p. 39, 2015.
- [3] Leichtbau BW GmbH, *Kostenanalyse Verschiedener Leichtbau-Verfahren Kostenanalyse Verschiedener Leichtbau-Verfahren*, Stuttgart, 2014.
- [4] H. Heuer, M. Schulze, M. Pooch, S. Gäbler, A. Nocke, G. Bardl, C. Cherif, M. Klein, R. Kupke, R. Vetter, F. Lenz, M. Kliem, C. Bülow, J. Goyvaerts, T. Mayer, and S. Petrenz, Review on quality assurance along the CFRP value chain – Non-destructive testing of fabrics, preforms and CFRP by HF radio wave techniques, *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 77, pp. 494–501, 2015.
- [5] X. L. Liu, P. J. Falzon, R. Sweeting, and R. Paton, Effective compressibility and permeability of multi-layer non-crimp fiberglass reinforcements, *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 861–879, 2004.
- [6] Y.-J. Lee, Y.-T. Jhan, C.-H. Chung, and Y. Hsu, A Prediction Method for In-Plane Permeability and Manufacturing Applications in the VARTM Process, *Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 691–699, 2011.
- [7] A. Kochan, *Untersuchungen zur zerstörungsfreien Prüfung von CFK-Bauteilen für die fertigungsbegleitende Qualitätssicherung im Automobilbau*, Technische Universität Dresden, 2011.
- [8] Q. Govignon, S. Bickerton, and P. A. Kelly, Simulation of the reinforcement compaction and resin flow during the complete resin infusion process, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 45–57, 2010.
- [9] T. Hermann, S. Bickerton, S. Van Oosterom, G. Lamb, and T. Henke, *Non-Destructive Evaluation of Preform Injectability and Compressibility for Quality Assessment in a Production Environment*, 2016, June, pp. 26–30.